

**Effective classroom management styles and teaching methods and
their rapport with students motivation and achievement :
Moroccan high school classrooms as a case study**

**Styles de gestion de classe et méthodes d'enseignement efficaces et
leur rapport avec la motivation des élèves: les classes secondaires
marocaines comme étude de cas**

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Résumé

La gestion de classe comprend une variété de compétences, de styles et de méthodes utilisés dans l'enseignement pour améliorer l'apprentissage et la motivation des élèves. Cet article vise à découvrir les différents styles utilisés par les enseignants afin de gérer efficacement leurs classes. La planification, l'organisation et la préparation font partie des compétences requises pour tout enseignement efficace. L'efficacité de l'enseignement repose sur la création de climats sains et productifs, dépourvus de tout problème disciplinaire. Cette étude examine également certains des principaux problèmes qui entravent le double processus d'enseignement et d'apprentissage. Cette étude est basée sur deux approches principales, à savoir les approches centrées sur l'élève comportementaliste et enseignant. Ils aident à reconnaître les moyens de promouvoir la qualité de l'enseignement et de l'apprentissage. Fournir des climats aux conditions optimales stimulerait et améliorerait le comportement, l'engagement et la motivation des élèves. Cette étude est principalement qualitative basée sur deux instruments principaux qui sont utilisés pour répondre aux questions de recherche qui sont l'ethnographie et les observations en classe. Ils sont utilisés pour tester les hypothèses de l'étude et pour aboutir à différentes conclusions. Les résultats montrent que les compétences et les principes de gestion de classe sont négligés, c'est pourquoi les mauvais comportements continuent de se produire.

Mot clés : Gestion ; comportement ; discipline ; motivation ; engagement

Abstract

Classroom management includes a variety of skills, styles and methods used in teaching to enhance students' learning and motivation. This paper aims at uncovering different styles used by teachers in order to manage their classrooms effectively. Planning, organization and preparation are among the skills that are required in any effective teaching. Teaching efficiency resides on the creation of healthy and productive climates devoid of any disciplinary issues. This study also examines some of the major issues that hinder the twin processes of teaching and learning. This study is based on two main approaches namely the behaviorist and teacher Vs student centered approaches. These help recognize ways of promoting the quality of teaching and learning. Providing climates with optimal conditions would both stimulate and improve students' behavior, engagement and motivation. This study is mainly qualitative based on two main instruments which are used to answer the research questions which are ethnography and classroom observations. They are used to test the hypotheses of the study and to reach different findings. Findings show that classroom management skills and principles are overlooked which is why misbehaviors keep occurring.

Keywords: Management, Misbehavior, Discipline, Motivation, Engagement

Introduction

Classroom management is an area of study that is of paramount importance in the field of teaching. Its effectiveness lies in its ways of providing safe and comfortable climates where motivating students and building their self esteem are practiced and encouraged. A variety of strategies and methods are used in different ways by educators. Each educator uses her / his own strategy to manage her /his classroom. However, these strategies are not considered as effective once disruption keeps happening. Dealing with daily disruption and helping students to be engaged and be on task in activities are among the principles of classroom management. Likewise, students' satisfaction and enjoyment come along the way. Additionally, students feel motivated and able to cooperate with one another. Classroom management is one of the main constituents in teaching English as a foreign language. Teaching and learning English would be a significant experience when optimal conditions are offered. Managing and maintaining classroom orders has been always conceived as a real challenge that may succumb teachers' profession. Teaching has been often conceived as a frustrating and unenjoyable journey. Some teachers along the years of teaching feel frustrated and therefore quit their profession due to various reasons namely students misbehavior; lack of motivation and so and so forth.

Frustration and discouragement on the teachers' part may only be the outcome of some methods and strategies deployed to deter classrooms' issues. Novice teachers are perhaps unaware of the ways classrooms are managed to put aside some recurring events namely disciplinary problems. Besides; a number of classrooms' aspects are overlooked when the only concern is to stop behavior rather than preventing it from occurring. Maintaining classrooms' order and discipline requires a great deal of preparation on the teachers' behalf. The quality of teaching and learning English as a foreign language per se is only promoted once preventive measures and strategies are enhanced and practiced. Henceforth, managing classrooms is a farfetched practice in the teaching process. Important classroom management practices are neglected while others are overstressed. Emphasizing control in a way that would influence students' attention remains a crucial factor. But this control goal should not be to the detriment to students' academic and emotional learning. As a matter of fact, classroom management goals and practices are to be reconsidered in order to reinforce and enhance classroom discipline and learning. To promote students demeanour and level of learning; the student centered approach has been always recommended. It both fosters

students autonomy and engagement in learning which leads consequently to the change of behavior.

Classroom management revolves around any strategy, any practice and goal that would produce environments conducive to learning. These strategies would both promote the learning quality and also help maintain classroom's order in the long run. Doyles provides an overall definition of classroom management. Classroom management is an umbrella concept that encompasses manifold strategies and pre-planned activities that would foster both students' learning and behavior.

The concept of classroom management has been broadened to encompass a number of important strategies and practices that would produce healthy learning climates. For him, classroom management practices includes also the maintenance of order and control but they are done in a smooth way. That is to say, through sets of activities planned by teachers, students' learning and behavior would be enhanced. In connection with this, this study would tackle the very complexity of classroom management. It examines a number of issues and styles of teachers so as to come up with new solutions and effective practices in managing classrooms. It highlights the very multidimensionality of classroom management. It requires teachers to be at once spontaneous and flexible towards unpredictable events.

The nature of classroom management is very complex in that it contains numbers of practices to be implemented to create healthy learning climates. However, the problems of this study revolve around several matters that keep happening in Moroccan public high schools. The processes of teaching and learning could be affected and deteriorated due to the absence of some important elements. These are embodied through teachers' personalities and styles, the availability of teaching materials and a healthy student-teacher interactions which play an influential role in ensuring productive environments.

This study aims at projecting and highlighting some disciplinary problems that occur in Moroccan public secondary schools. In order to achieve this aim, a limited number of public high schools were singled out as case studies. This choice would reflect and mirror today's classroom situations. In line with this, the purpose of this study is two fold. First, it draws attention to the causes that emanate from ineffective teaching and management styles Second, it aims at finding ways for preventing classroom problems in an innovative way which is

adaptable to the Moroccan context. Besides this, It clarifies how misbehavior is accentuated due to some classroom practices as well as the consequences that accompany such problems.

This study is an attempt to test two main hypotheses concerning the quality of teaching and learning processes. The hypotheses tend to assess the quality of both processes at various levels namely: at the level of teaching practices, styles used to manage and handle disciplinary problems, then at the level of the physical and the emotional climates and their relation with students' performance, achievement, motivation and adjustment of their own behavior.

The first hypothesis assumes that teachers' ways of giving instructions and delivering lessons may have a great impact on students' engagement, performance and achievement. The rationale behind this expectation is that classrooms are considered as educational contexts where students and teachers interact. Henceforth, decisions and plans which are made by teachers should match the students' demands and needs. These decisions will more strongly affect students' achievement and motivation. Students then are more able to receive their teachers' input.

The second hypothesis revolves around the fact that physical and emotional climates are in a complementary relationship. In other words, the physical conditions are not sufficient in catering for students' needs. They are only productive when the emotional aspect is enhanced. The physical and the emotional aspect of classrooms can affect to a large extent students' performance and adjustment of their behavior. Teachers' practices are best carried out when the necessary physical conditions are met. The physical conditions include the space as well as the class size. When class size is smaller, students then are likely to perform well and have self control over their own behavior. The emotional aspect also counts as it fosters students' learning. The emotional aspect is shown through daily interactions that occur in classrooms between teachers and students.

This study raises a number of important questions on which investigation and analysis are based. They are as follows :

1. To what extent do the physical and the emotional environments influence students' behavior and motivation to learn ?
2. Are disciplinary issues linked to teachers' ways of giving instructions?

3. Do the uncatered students' needs be, them emotional, linguistic or physical needs and language learning weaknesses , raise disciplinary matters ?
4. Do classroom management strategies influence students' motivation, engagement and language learning ? What are the main factors that have an impact on the above three variables ?

The upcoming chapters constitute the framework of this study. The review of the literature aims at providing a coherent understanding of old and new models about teaching and learning applied beforehand by prominent scholars and theorists. The literature is considered as a guidance for this research and as an answer to its questions. Furthermore, this paper shows the methodological approach used and different findings of the qualitative methods that aim at highlighting different styles of management used by teachers and their effects on students motivation and achievement.

1 . Review of the literature

1.1 Conceptualizing Classroom management

Teaching has been long considered as a process which is basically centered on managing and maintaining discipline with long term effect strategies and techniques in classrooms. A variety of techniques and methods are proved to provide suitable learning environments and opportunities to learn. Providing adequate learning contexts are among the key components of classroom management. Scrivener (2005) is among the scholars who strived to give clear definitions of classroom management and its impact on students' achievement. Scrivener lists two important elements that work under the heading of classroom management namely conditions and teachers' skills. For starters, conditions refer to the climate within which learning takes place. Second, teachers' skills stand for the ways multiple teaching tasks and lessons are organized and planned(Scrivener, 2005, 79).

It is assumed that both elements have a cause and effect relationship. In other words, climates are only productive when instructions are given effectively. Simply put, ineffective intructions and lack of organizational skills can be to the detriment of any learning conditions. Scrivener also refers implicitly to different roles undertaken by teachers. They oscillate between facilitators, knowledge transmitters and managers. Managing classrooms is among the most challenging and prerequisite job that is to be reconsidered so as to create suitable environments alongside with the acquisitions of enough teaching skills. Likewise, students'

learning and achievement are promoted and enhanced. Conditions refer to the emotional or the psycho-physical environments. These kind of environments are more about the building of healthy relationships between teachers and students. This eventually will lead to high students' achievement and performance at both academic and social levels.

The classroom is not only considered as a setting or a mere place. It is also a context where students interact and socialize with one another. The main objective of classroom management is to foster a sense of community and connection among educators and their learners. Teaching is an umbrella process which includes important elements ranging from curriculum content, instructional materials and resources, the physical and emotional climates to students and teachers' relationships. All these elements represent the backbone and the very essence of any ideal classroom. Building healthy rapports between students and teachers can make a difference in teaching especially when it comes to learning a second language. Establishing good rapports means simply developing positive relations between teachers and students. Teachers are not only concered with giving instructions but also with making balances between their responsibilities and relationship building since teaching remains an interactive process per see. That is to say, it is mainly based on interactions and communication.

Engaging students can be dealt with through a number of procedures like building healthy emotional climates as well as creating classroom activities that would both stimulate students' attention and behavior. Maintaining students' attention is one of teachers' preoccupations at the beginning of their lessons. Teaching does not only have to do with the curriculum or the lesson content. It has to do also with engaging students and triggering their interests which sometimes should precede content. Ryan (2006) refers to different aspects of classroom management like maintaining students' attention to lessons, engagement and behavior. These factors widen the scope of classroom management. Ryan stresses the importance of raising students' engagement in the lesson. In other terms, different ways are to be taken into account in order to have students interested in the subject(2015 :177).

Roughly speaking, Ryan encourages students' engagement in classroom activities and instructions. Students' attention should be held before the beginning of each lesson. Additionally, holding students' attention can be done through making them involved in decision making like deciding upon activities that they desire to learn etc. Ryan relates both

engagement and student teacher relationships to behavior. In other terms, the adjustment of behavior could happen naturally when students are endowed with enough support and care from their teachers.

Ryan gives effective strategies that lead to the prevention of disciplinary problems. Keeping students on task should be at the top of teachers' concerns. In so doing, daily problems are alleviated. Ryan also clarifies the fact that students regulate their own behaviors when classrooms are transformed into communities where they feel they belong to. Scrivener and Ryan provide coherent understandings of what constitutes a good classroom management. It is basically done through several steps namely a good rapport between teacher and students, conditions of learning, students' engagement and behavior. These areas are to be taken into consideration to have consistency in both learning and teaching processes.

1.2 Models of discipline : Traditional approaches :

Several scholars were innovative in their ways of thinking about discipline. Eric Berne, Thomas Harris, Ginott and Kounin to name just a few were considered as the pioneers of the field of classroom management. They all proposed and called for the implementation of several models that ranged from low, medium to high control approaches. These approaches were meant to maintain order and gain control over children's educational life.

- **Low control approaches :** The development of such approaches was due to the inventiveness of numerous scholars namely : Eric Berne (1950), Thomas Harris (1995), Haim Ginott (1965), and Redl and Wattenberg (1951). These theorists all agreed upon a common point, which is the students' ability to assume their responsibility in controlling their own behaviors.

Much concerns were given to Berne's theory as it constitutes a fundamental part in dealing with human interactions in general and student and teachers in particular. Transactional analysis is a theory based on the fact that behavior is understood and analysed only through the transaction that occurs between individuals. This theory shows that human beings keep switching from different states within their selves so that they can meet their own needs and solve their problems. Transactional analysis was an approach first developed by the Canadian psychiatrist Eric Berne (1950). This was based mainly on the assumptions that each person is responsible for his/her own behaviors, feelings and thoughts. Berne notices that the brain is

responsible for recording things that the human being experienced which enables him/her to remember (Zwermer, 2005 :208). The human brain is considered as a storage device. It is rather a machine which store information and situations in a permanent way. It works wherever the individual undergoes similar situations at different point in time to help him or her recall by keeping the same feeling. The human brain manages not only to memorize images but also different emotions that an individual had at that moment of happening. Berne indicates also the ways we as individuals relate to things or persons. The individual feeling is highly linked to his / her interaction with another person. Through his/ her transaction, his / her memory is brought back to work and the feeling is identified. Hence, The feeling be it negative or positive could affect the relationships among individuals. This can lead to either tensions or mutual understanding between persons.

Berne's approach refers to the power of interaction in consolidating relationships between individuals. In order to have a cross understanding among individuals, educators should be aware of the parts that constructs students' personalities. Each behavior reflects one's own inner self either the child, the parent or the adult..Dymbye and Harisson (2008) conceive of as an alternative approach to the management of behavioral issues(2008:131). Teachers always play neutral roles in enhancing and changing students' behaviors. Berne's Theory appears to change the dynamics of classroom management at the level of discipline by encouraging interactions and conversations. Likewise, positive climates are developed within classrooms. Though Transactional Analysis has a positive influence on both students' behavior and the rapport between teachers and students, it seems to be a complex and a time-consuming method. Transactional analysis can be a worthwhile strategy to overcome daily classroom matters. Hence, this method should be applied in a meticulous way in order to see its effectiveness. Transactional analysis remains a theory with short term effect once it is not practiced and rehearsed. A mastery of such a method would lead to a better understanding of recent events and daily transactions.

- **Medium control approaches** Unlike the low teacher control approaches , these approaches put an emphasis on the importance of the group's needs over the individual's. Rudolf Dreikurs(1964), Albert Nelson (1996), Glasser(1948), Kounin(1977) introduced a number of models that were the cornerstone of classroom management. They were the forefathers of classroom management

and discipline. They established several notions that were effective in handling students' behavior.

The Kounin's model : Kounin(1970) brought about techniques and strategies that can be used to prevent any disciplinary problems from taking place. They are as follows : the ripple effect, withitness, overlapping, smoothness, group focus, satiation.

For Kounin, students who witness teachers' actions towards their colleagues tend to behave appropriately. In other words, teachers' actions have an effect on other students' behaviors. They learn from others' mistakes Martella,2012 :16).. The ripple effect is Kounin's technique to prevent daily disciplinary problems from occurring. It is a technique used to help teachers manage flexibly their students' behavior without having to rectify students' misbehavior one by one. In other words, the correction of students' behavior can eventually impact the behavior of other students. However, the ripple effect does not have to do only with correcting misbehaviors but it can be also as an encouraging method for other students. A teacher may sometimes encourage a student for her/his adequate behavior. This strategy can be an incentive for other students to behave adequately. These terms refer to a set of behaviors that a teacher should avoid during the lesson for maintaining classroom order and holding student's attention. For Kounin, good transitions require clear directions, fluidity in drawing students' attention to the lesson. Effective transitions would contribute into students' engagement in the lesson. These transitions refer to the steps and activities teachers undertake in order to provide instructions devoid of any flaws nor gaps. Kounin's terms refer to a set of interruptions that keep occurring in classrooms which are the main causes of students' inattentiveness and misbehavior. This is why the smoothness of lesson is of paramount important in that it keeps students engaged. For Kounin, Successful teachers are those who apply smooth transitions during their lessons and provide a variety of activities which are thematically related. They do not spend much time nor dwell on details so as to avoid disruptions and gain control over their students.

- **High control approaches**

These approaches bring about new notions that eliminate the students' self control of their own behaviors. External conditions are the only incentives for students' growth and development. The high teacher control approaches are foregrounded on the behaviorist belief. This belief assumes that behaviors are only strengthened or weakened by rewards and

punishment. In this respect, prominent theorists and practitioners contributed to a large extent in representing important principles of classroom management namely : Fredric Jones(1987), Skinner(1953), Canter(2002), Engelmann and Dobson (1983).

- Operant conditionning: A technique developed by the prominent Psychologist B:F Skinner (1988). Skinner's technique is based mainly on the behaviorist's point of view. Behaviors are conditioned by the consequences that come after. The consequences make either the behavior reinforced or weakened. For Skinner 2008:53, Operant conditionning is based on the premise that all actions that are reinforced by consequences are more likely to take place later. However, behaviors that are weakened by the consequences tend to be eliminated in the long run. This is how individuals learn how to operate within their environment. As its name indicate, operant conditioning means simply that behaviors is only adjusted and operated by the presence of some conditions that either strengthen or weaken them.

Skinner's four types of operant conditionning indicate that consequences as well as rewards are the only means of reinforcement of behavior. Conversely, punishment and extinction may weaken and stop behaviors. Skinner offers different types of conditionning to imply that rewards as reinforcers may only be suitable for some category of people while they may not work for others. It means that reinforcement should be used at the idiosyncratic level. In other words, a teacher should vary his rewards according to students' needs and preferences. B.F Skinner differentiates between two types of behavior which are respondent and operant. Both types of behavior occur by either the presence or the removal of rewards as kinds of reinforcement. In other words, respondent behavior happens as the result of a stimuli, whereas the latter takes place naturally and spontaneously by organism. He provides also some key elements in his theory which are negative and positive reinforcement. Changing behavior either by offering or omitting rewards may improve the person's internal motivation. In the case of deprivation and removal of rewards, a person sometimes tends to change his behavior accordingly.

Skinner's theory contributes to a large extent to the field of education. It explains in a way or another some aspects of behavior. However, it has overlooked several issues concerning the human being's capacities. Eysenck shows clearly that Skinner's theory was mainly based on the study of animals' behaviors rather than human beings'. According to Eysenck, this theory

is only applicable on non human species in some situations (Skinner, 1958: 29). Human beings are distinguished from other species at the level of language. It is an important part which was neglected in Skinner's theory. For Eysenck, learning is a complex process which requires a great deal of work on teachers' part to come up with new techniques and methods suitable for learners.

Theories that were developed beforehand by psychologists and educators made considerable contributions in various fields including education. Low to medium teacher control approaches are fruitful and beneficial. They encourage positive ways in dealing with students' misbehaviors. They are concerned with increasing students' motivation and engagement. Also, they are aimed at promoting student-teacher rapport. Unlike high teacher control approaches, several techniques have been proven to be inadequate in developing students' capacities of learning and self-regulation of their own behavior. High control teacher approaches were based on motivating students extrinsically by rewards. These techniques were inefficient as they render students passive in handling their responsibilities.

2. Research Methodology

This study made use of qualitative data. It was implemented via the application of observation. Observational data were reduced. The reduction was done according to their relevance to my research questions and subquestions. This enabled me to manage easily the data. Data were represented and displayed via transcription. Transcribing interactions facilitated the analysis process. It helps delineate some important aspects about the studied phenomenon.

As said earlier, the research project is primarily qualitative in that it made use of different instruments like ethnography and classroom observations. The classes I observed varied from common core, first year to second year baccalaureat. Two main reasons were behind the attendance of such classes. These reasons have to do with research purpose and questions. The first reason is to have a deep knowledge of classroom management styles and also teachers' strategies to provide an environment adequate for learning.

The second reason is to see the major issues that are behind students' misbehavior. Simply put, it is meant to shed light on whether there is a correlation between teachers' ways of giving instructions and these disciplinary problems. In so doing, some teachers provided me

with their time tables. It was possible for me to attend their classes. Sometimes, they proposed to me to attend the classes that would be of much benefit for my research project. Some teachers saw my research as a burden and did not want me to have access to their classes. Eventually, four teachers were willing to partake in the fieldwork. The selected classes represented some behavior features ranging from average to inappropriate. The table below provides clearly the population of this study which encompasses teachers, students and administrators who work either in public or private secondary schools in Fez. It is the following:

Number of Moroccan secondary schools	Five schools : two private secondary schools and three public secondary schools
Classes	Thirty three out of forty classes in the overall classroom observations
Teachers	Two private secondary school teachers Three public school teachers
Administrators	Two private secondary school administrators Three public school administrators
Students	In private secondary schools: 30 students per class In Public secondary schools: up to 45 students per class
Number of hours and months	132 hours within five months
Kind of classes	Common core, first year and second year baccalaureate students

Source : Auteur

Since ethnographic observations are transcribed and rendered into written formats, the researcher should deal with them via applying text analysis. Porter provides some basic steps undertaken to cover various aspects of a text. Texts are approached by their language so that they can be described and analysed(2012 :32). Text analysis means a systematic process via which researchers can manage their data easily. Eventually, data were read and re read in order to get familiarized with. Data were classified according to their thematic similarities. The division of data into categories and groups provided me with clear insights of my research project. This study dealt in the first place with issues undergone by teachers and students. Motivation is an umbrella theme that encompasses a number of issues namely : Traditional styles of giving instructions and their relation to disengagement, passivity and misbehavior, English as a foreign language, motivation, teachers' styles of managing disciplinary problems and lack of time management.

3 . Results and discussions of findings

3.1 To what extent teachers' instruction can affect students' motivation and achievement.

Students' motivation and achievement are among the major aspects of classroom management. Students' learning, motivation and achievement are affected by the ways instructions are given, presented and how lessons are planned. This study revealed that most Moroccan secondary teachers rely on Teacher centered approach. This indicates that students' motivation and achievement are hindered by classroom's monotony and every day routine. Performing the same teaching tasks in the same way deteriorates students' engagement and motivation. Variety in all aspects of lessons enlivens and energizes students' learning. Variety can be applied via the use of supplementary materials and some teaching aids.

The study also showed that teachers' high level of competency and proficiency should be beyond any poor conditions under which the language is taught. Teachers are seen also to be enablers and diagnosticians. Ineffectiveness is directly related to teachers' inability to handle learning problems and environmental hindrances. Diagnosing students' amotivation and lack of achievement are among the basics of any effective teaching. The finding is similar to Socket (1988), in his statement he defines education as the endeavor to get people to do things they could not previously do, to understand things they could

not previously understand and perhaps to become the people they did not expect to become.” (Quoted in Rumbert , 1999, 195)

Socket’s quote puts the concept of motivation into broader context which is not restricted to only tests and lessons. He mentions the fact that teachers have the primacy and priority to help students’ develop their motivational qualities. They should inspire them and make them able to learn on their own. This study also found out that both teachers and schools contribute to a large extent to the building of climates and atmospheres. Engagement and motivation are reinforced through the use of various methods and techniques. These techniques would aspire and lead to independent learning and goals’ achievement.

Intrinsic or extrinsic motivation should be fostered by teachers at the first place since they remain the cornerstone of the educational system. The study showed also that innovative teaching techniques are not sufficient when it comes to learning a foreign language. Enhancing students’ communication skills , building healthy rapports between students and teachers and catering for students’ needs and styles are also of paramount importance. These aspects should be all intertwined in order to create adequate learning contexts. Likewise, all students are able and feel free to communicate and express themselves adequately and spontaneously. They can control and regulate their own behaviors. Self regulation of one’s own behavior and high level of achivement are only the results of a good classrom management that is implemented.

The above mentioned aspects represent the essence of any effective teaching. This finding is similar to Anderman (2013) who perceived classroom management as the gatkeeper of learning and is framed by social , cultural and instructional and organizational contexts. It provides teachers and students with opportunity to participate and build a positive framework of interpersonal and academic interactions. As teaching , learning and society in general become more complex. Classroom management provide as source to navigate this complexity. The term is often used synonymously with students’ behavior and discipline and spans a continuum from compliance and obedience to student reflection and self disicpline. Students’ achievement may be one result of classroom management because effective management enables the teaching and learning process within the unique educational social context. (2013 : 228)

3.2 To what extent teachers' styles of managing classrooms can alleviate daily disciplinary problems.

The study aimed at representing teachers' reactions vis à vis disciplinary problems and their maintenance of order in classrooms. In other words, the study's main focus was on teachers' actions towards creating suitable learning climates. The study findings and analysis support the prediction of the hypothesis which assumes that management styles could affect learners performance, motivation and reduce disciplinary problems. A healthy and a productive classroom management requires order and control. However, settling classroom rules and principles remain prerequisite despite the variety of techniques and methods used by teachers to cater for their students' preferences. In these contexts where order and control are settled, learning and respect keep reigning. The study revealed that the styles of managing their classrooms are somehow alike. The authoritative style is often used in classrooms. In the Moroccan educational system, this style seems to operate so as to decrease daily classroom matters on a daily basis. As said in the analytical part, styles vary from authoritative, authoritarian to permissive ones. These three predominant styles may all seem familiar to students. These are most of the time imposed to by their parents. For them, imposing control and deciding upon rewards and consequences following each demeanour are among the things that help maintain order at home.

However, it was found that teachers who used the authoritative way of handling classroom's issues are the ones who desire compliance and obedience. Students are not given the opportunity to regulate their own behavior and be more autonomous. Similar findings were reported by Mccown (2012) who stated that teachers who opt for an authoritarian style are likely to have student compliance rather than autonomy. Teachers who adopt a permissive style are likely to rely heavily on students' identifying with and respecting them as their main approach to classroom management (Do what I say because you like me and respect my judgement). Teachers who adopt an authoritative style are likely to want their students to learn to eventually regulate their own behavior. By explaining the rationale for classroom rules and adjusting those rules as students demonstrate the ability to govern themselves appropriately. (2012 :261)

Mccown findings alluded to the fact that the authoritative style remains at the top of any other styles since it helps maintain classroom discipline. It also provide a respectful

environment where students learn and regulate their own behavior with enough autonomy and self motivation. This study has attempted to demonstrate that teachers who use the authoritative style are the ones who have classrooms that function well at the level of order and control and also at the level of academic achievement. Such environments help students develop their intrinsic motivation. This finding suggested that the authoritative style allow students to be more autonomous in a restricted way. That is to say, teachers should always stand by their students and keep monitoring their behaviors. Kounin's famous concept which is Withitness was proven to be an effective method in dealing with disciplinary matters. This study showed that by using withitness, a teacher is more willing to prevent misbehavior from occurring. Kounin emphasized the fact that teachers who prove to their students that they know what is going on in a classroom (the legendary teacher with eyes in the back of his head) usually have fewer behavior problems than teachers who appear to be unaware of potentially disruptive behavior. With it teachers will prevent small problems from becoming large ones by staring at a misbehaving student with a firm facial expression or by making a quick comment about focusing on the task at hand (2012 :262)

Kounin gathered important elements in order to optimize learning and teaching. Among these important component are non verbal communication and eye contact. Non verbal communication should exist in everyday teaching. Besides this, eye contact can help develop healthy relationships between students and teachers. The data findings showed also that misbehavior keeps occurring in secondary schools because the withitness techniques are not used. Some teachers found it hard and a bit challenging when it comes to manage their classrooms particularly in gaining students' attention. The loss of attention represented the very common disciplinary problem in most Moroccan EFL classrooms. Students lose their attention basically when the lesson is not of interest to them or hard to be grasped. At this stage, the attention loss becomes a serious issue which needs to be handled.

This study findings tried to show that cooperative learning or working in groups is an effective strategy for both teachers and students. For the teacher, group work is tempting and challenging at the same time. It requires a high level of classroom management and control especially when dealing with disciplinary problems that arise during that time. For students, it is a worthwhile strategy. Keeping students on task makes them more self engaged and involved. Data findings also showed that group work can affect positively students' learning,

performance and achievement. It makes them practice the language with their peers without any apprehension. They can learn from each other as they feel motivated and eager to learn. The study also revealed that teachers ,who are able to apply this strategy have orderly classrooms. In such classrooms, students are able to communicate and express themselves freely and spontaneously.

Clements(1991) also found out that well planned cooperative work in small groups has an essential part to play in developing emotional and social competences, such as empathy, listening , sensitivity , negotiation, conflict, resolution and cooperation. It tends naturally to lead to an increase in the fun level in the classroom which can be encouraged through the use of laughter and give a sense of group responsibility for keeping the game going. (quoted in Weare : 2012 : 117) Clements and Johnson findings proved that group learning is considered as a key technique in the twin processes of teaching and learning. It can alleviate tension, boredom and routine in the long run. Teenagers always want to learn in a new way. This help them to be more receptive of daily instructions. Findings also showed that group work requires to be planned in order to avoid chaos and reduce daily issues. The data finding finally showed that working in groups is beneficial at the social level. Students become empathetic and respectful towards their classmates. Empathy makes them more unified and develop a sense of belonging within their classrooms and also within their society.

3.3 To what extent students are intrinsically motivated to learn a foreign language. Is their motivation only linked to achievement or the other way around.

The interpretation of data supported the prediction of the hypothesis that assumes that second language learning and teaching impact students' motivation and behavior. The findings aimed at providing used strategies and uncovering the daily disciplinary challenges in the classroom. The study revealed that learning English as a foreign language in Moroccan public high schools is practically linked to achievement. Achieving more often indicates students' progress and engagement according to teachers as well as school administrations .

However, neglecting other factors is the reason behind which students keep misbehaving. These factors are embodied through teachers' instructions first and then the environment . The study revealed that disciplinary problems emerge from the fact that classrooms ,as formal contexts , restrict students' performance and engagement. They are less willing to achieve.

Using a Guided discovery strategy develop students' self exploration of new things and ideas spontaneously. Though at a certain stage in learning , a student is unaware of some important details concerning the activity done in the target language. This would be better done through applying it rather in a meticulous way. This study findings attempted to show that exerting control in the classroom are widely predominant in most high schools whereas some innovative techniques for more productive and comfortable climates for students are overlooked. The study findings revealed that high achievers are more valorized and privileged than others in most Moroccan public high schools. To be academically distinguished in learning a language repartitions English into two levels namely the academic and the social ones. The academic language can be referred to as the language we learn and the social language is basically the language we acquire in our childhood which is not linked to either achievement or marks. Similar to these findings , Nino explained them more clearly in his findings, he stated that all faculty members should be aware of the basic differences between social language development and academic language development. The social language is more easily acquired than the academic language. Social language includes survival English or playground English. In other words, everyday English students use with friends, hear on TV or use in other informal setting. (2011: 43)

Krashen (1982) also estimated that social language development take one to two years with language experiences dictating how quickly it actually develop. Academic language is the language of the classroom and of content. This language takes five to seven years to acquire. If appropriate linguistic scaffolds are not in place, academic language develop ment can take much longer. But if the scaffolds are in place, it can occur more quickly (Nino :2011 : 43) .Nino and Krash findings showed that both social and academic language differ in terms of context and content. It is this formality that make academic language harder to learn. Students can hardly communicate since they are not exposed to authentic situations. This represents the overarching importance and effectiveness of social language since it is not context bound and it can be grasped spontaneously. Whereas academic language learning can only happen adequately if conditions meet the need of students. Krash and Nino refers indirectly to the fact that academic language is highly borned with some factors that render students achievement and motivation impossible and unattained.

Data findings strived to demonstrate that disciplinary problems emerge just because of the foreignness of the language. For students, English has no similarities with their native

language. Contrasts are engendered at various levels be them linguistic, cultural etc. So the least teachers can do is to provide students with suitable formal contexts. Classrooms are places replete with opportunities to learn, activities to do, and new things to discover. Formal contexts are judged to be productive once teachers know how to teach English as a foreign language innovatively. EFL students should first and foremost love and appreciate the language so as to be engaged, motivated and more autonomous to regulate their behaviors. Students more often receive information passively when learning other subjects. EFL teachers should then go beyond their students' expectation when it comes to learning a foreign language.

EFL students may not expect teachers to give instructions in a traditional way nor receiving orders. Teachers should be more of guides and facilitators than lecturers. The study findings revealed also that a foreign language should be taught innovatively. In that way, EFL classrooms will be devoid of any disciplinary problems and troublesome situations will also lessen. Bandura's findings support the third objective about achievement, motivation and second language learning(1995 :106). He presumed that learning a target language by following these principles would impact and influence both students' achievement and behavior. By identifying methods and strategies that suit best their students, teachers can resolve and overcome the issues of discipline coherently and effectively. In the same respect, Gardner (1985) also provided five constructs which he claimed to be effective when learning or acquiring a second language.

Gardener's constructs have a considerable effect on second language learning and achievement (Flemens 2009 : 96). For Gardner, these five key constructs represent some of the motivational factors that lead students either to move forward in his /her learning a language or to refrain from doing so. Refraining from learning a foreign language can be behind some external elements like fear from making mistakes or from others' reactions vis á vis his or her performance precisely from their peers and teachers. Gardner extended the concept of motivation when learning a second language. Building on the above five constructs, students would be then able to improve their own learning strategies and show a high level of achievement as well as performance. For him, these variables go beyond the dichotomous division of motivation that are either intrinsic or extrinsic. Bandura's joins Gardner's principles by displaying the SIT model which revolves around methods that stimulate behavioral change such as motivation and self perception, focuses on the strategies

learners use to become self regulated in their learning. The factors related to this theory have been found to have an influence on second or foreign language learning performance.(quoted in Flemens : 2009 : 96).

3.4 To indicate that time management represents a challenge also to teachers when dealing with disciplinary problems. Would effective time management lead to the reduction of such matters and to the improvement of students' engagement and motivation to learn.

The hypothesis prediction was realised in the sense that it reflected daily realities of classrooms. It tackled the issue of time management and its impact on students achievement as well as on behavior. Considering the data analysis and interpretation of data, findings presumed that time management is primarily centered around providing enough time and opportunities to learn a foreign language. Besides the scarcity of materials and environment conditions, there existed also the issue of not endowing students with a large amount of engaged time. As said earlier, time is divided into three components namely the allocated , engaged and the academic time. The study findings showed that all these types are interrelated. If one type is overlooked by teachers then opportunities to learn will gradually diminish or at the very least be absent. Some types of time are overlooked because of some teachings practices and methods that push students to be neither engaged , nor motivated but rather retarded and ill behaved.

The study finding demonstrated also that students are provided with opportunities to misbehave rather than learn and benefit from daily instructions. Similarly, Hicks(2003) found out and developed a strategy that may once regulate students' behavior and increase academic achievement. He suggested that filling in the time by varying instructional strategies with block scheduling, which provides opportunities to use multiple instructional strategies during the same class period. (2003:51). For Hicks, setting up schedules should be done in light of students' need and learning opportunities. In other terms, English teaching period has to be exploited and invested through lessons' and instructions variety. Handling teaching time is one of the major component in classroom management that works both for the benefit of teachers and students. They both would consider that this very little period of time should be invested in learning and not wasted because of some external factors. Scheduling is a kind of a preventive strategy that would not block teachers' career or student's performance and behavior

Similar to Hicks' finding, the study seeks out to show that classroom management does not only rest on rules, principles and routines but also on a well managed time in a way that will be beneficial for students' growth and development with higher academic achievement. The findings of the study have proven that there is a tremendous rapport between time management and students' academic performance. Most of public high schools witnessed a large amount of time's waste. Teachers keeps complaining because of shortage of time. They feel unable to compensate what was wasted. They do not know that what is wasted it is not students' time but students' loss of interest and lack of attention on the studied subject.

Misbehavior and disciplinary problems are to be interpreted as flaws that may exist when time is ill managed. Benjamin Franklin (1994) states that lost time is never found again, consider the teacher who loses the first second minutes at the beginning of class in getting students settled down and another minute in taking attendance and who also gives students the last two or three minutes at the end of the period to do homework or get ready to pass to the next class. Not including additional lost time for other outside disturbances such as phone calls announcement and late students with or without pass, it is not common for teachers to lose six minutes of instructional minutes over 180 days. That is an entire month lost to non instructional time. Time that could be used to engage students with inquiry. (Quoted in Llewellyn :2005 :100)

Franklin's findings provided clear insights about how time is lost at public high schools. His findings join the study interpretation in that it stresses the fact of teachers unawareness of how this lost amount of time can detrimental to students' achievement and behavior. Franklin added in his quote that time loss represents a usual variable for teachers which is taken for granted. The study findings suggested that time should be used wisely. It should endow students with more and enough instructional time. Despite some daily disruptions, teachers should know how to control their time and not the other way around.

3.5 To what extent students' engagement and performace can be affected by class size and how it is challenging for teachers to deal with such matters

The study finding endeavored to see that class size plays an important role in influencing the quality of teaching and learning. This study findings reflects upon the fact that students' learning development and behavior adjustment is not only linked to teachers' instructions but

also to how large and small classes are. According to data analysis and interpretations, it has been assumed that class size has a great impact first on teachers as they can spontaneously implement different strategies and create environments conducive to learning. Second, students perform well, feel comfortable and able to be self autonomous and adjust their own behaviors. The study findings set out to demonstrate that students' inattention is just the effect of large classes on their learning. Making comparisons between two categories of schools was a way to see the major discrepancies that exist between them and reflect upon the significance of class size on both learning and teaching. Related to this study findings, several researchers have argued about the class size and its effect on both teachers and students. Both Shamin(1996) and Kumar (1992) share different findings about class size per se. Beginning with Shamin (1996) , he found out that in practical terms, the physical constraints of large class teaching such as the difficulties teachers experience trying to move around overcrowded classrooms to promote learner interaction or provide learners with enough individual attention , do create specific challenges for establishing and maintaining L2 learning opportunities. “(1992:2)

Shamin's finding provided several disadvantages that accompany large classes. He mentioned that physical environments including the number of students always represent a real constraint and challenge for teachers. Moving around easily and delivering instructions in an appropriate way can not be implemented when classes are crowded. For Shamin, learning a second language is better practiced in environments where students' number is limited. In language classes which include small number of students, more opportunities and attention are provided. Shamin also pinpoints to the fact that teaching and learning difficulties are related to class size. Shamin seems to encourage class size reduction as a suitable and a desirable condition for all teachers and students. In small classes, all opportunities are available namely the one to one instruction, teachers are able to know their students better and identify their learning development and deficiencies instantaneously and easily looking for remedies. Opposite to Shamin' finding, Kumar's finding assumed that class size should not be considered as a hindrance for teachers. Class size as a physical condition should be alleviated by teachers' strategies and the general atmosphere that reign in classrooms regardless of students' numbers.

He argued that it is the nature of the teaching learning activities and the teachers' role and attitude which influences the nature of learner participation and the patterns of interaction rather than class size per se. “(1992:2)

Kumar's finding goes counter to Shamin's as he insists on the fact that physical contexts should not represent any constraints for the teaching and learning processes. For Kumar, regardless of the number of issues that may face students in order to pursue their learning, teachers possess different methods and strategies that would alleviate the classroom daily tensions which basically centers around class size. In the above quote, Kumar put the full responsibility on teachers not on environment. The role that teachers assume in their classes is the only source of influence on students' learning and achievement. Students can put up with physical constraints when teachers' proficiency and ability to transform classes into effective communities no matter how big they are. For Kumar, in large classes, interactions and communication are possible when there are activities which enhance students' skills and needs.

Conclusions and recommendations

Classrooms are formal platforms that should initiate effective learning with suitable pedagogical strategies. They should be designed also to enhance students' learning, capacities and styles. These environments should work out students' engagement and involvement in the learning process. This section discussed and gave a summary of the study findings. It provided also clear insights about how hard the teaching career is. It showed that classrooms' life is not easy. Succumbing the classrooms' flaws by teachers render learning possible for language learners.

This chapter emphasized the fact that classroom management is a field that is concerned more on preventing disciplinary matters and daily issues undergone either by teachers or students. Classroom management is conceived of as an immunitary system that would guard against any abrupt flaws which are hindering students' learning. Being provided with effective weapons to face daily teaching matters, teachers should not forget to be humane at first place by considering each student as a special case and by treating them individually and equally.

A classroom management remains an idiosyncratic issue. Each teacher is in need of management plan that suits the level, desire and demands of students. Teachers are responsible for engaging, organizing and managing their students. In so doing, a teacher should develop their own personality by not combining it with school values. A personality that is replete with fun, patience and care would stimulate students' responsibility and also

create a positive classroom environment. Last but not least, it would maximize time of learning opportunities. Henceforth, the combination and the practice of theories and models like Skinners', Redl and Watterberg's are at once effective and encouraging for students. This could fine tune students' demeanour. Redl and Wattenberg's theorz about group dynamics seemed to be fruitful and beneficial for teachers as it is in line with the cooperative learning approach and have a situational assistance concept. In other words, teachers often opt for Watterberg's theory as it assists and helps teachers overcome their daily disciplinary issues.

Teachers would simply address any minor disruptive and aggressive behaviors in their classroom management plan in order to teach and impose discipline. They should first and foremost prevent the fire before they have to put it out. Some teachers would not be willing to address each minor issue but at least students would realize the consequence that their behavior have on others. Treating students fairly is another important factor in dealing with disciplinary issues. Teachers should treat students as individuals because students are all different. Each student has differing abilities, cultures and ethnicities etc. It is preferable that teachers spend more time with troublemakers and slow learners. Instructions should vary according to students' preferences and levels.

Interacting with students would help them feel safe and comfortable. In this way, their emotional and social development are fostered. Last but not least, teachers need to reflect constantly upon their teaching instructions, daily situations and see from where the problem stems. A thorough meditation on their own strategies and performance encourage teachers to identify and modify their weaknesses.

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